

The approximate solution of nonlinear Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations of fractional order

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Abstract. Fractional nonlinear Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations are solved by using the Bessel polynomials. At first, we introduced Bessel functions and the transfer matrix basis from Bessel functions to Taylor polynomials. Then, we obtain the operational matrix of fractional order integration and this matrix is utilized to reduce the fractional Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations to system of algebraic equations. The present study in comparison with other methods shows that when these methods are applied to nonlinear FVIDEs of fractional order is more accurate, efficiency and reliability.

Keywords: Bessel polynomials; Fractional Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equation; Fractional operational matrix

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1 Introduction

The fractional calculus have attracted a lot of researchers and scientists. Researchers discuss on fractional calculus in various fields of science and engineering such as fluid mechanics, viscoelasticity, biology, physics and engineering applications, for more details see [1, 2]. In this paper will be taken the nonlinear integro-differential equations of fractional order with a Caputo fractional derivative [3], let us consider the general form of nonlinear FVIDEs of fractional order:

$${}_x D^\alpha y(x) = g(x) + \lambda_f \int_0^1 k_f(x, t) \psi_f(t, y(t)) dt + \lambda_v \int_0^x k_v(x, t) \psi_v(t, y(t)) dt, \quad 0 \leq x, t \leq 1, \quad n-1 < \alpha \leq n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (1)$$

under the mixed conditions

$$y^{(i)}(0) = \delta_i, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1, \quad (2)$$

where ${}_x D^\alpha$ is Caputos fractional derivative and α is a parameter describing the order of fractional derivative. Also, $\psi_f(t, y(t))$ and $\psi_v(t, y(t))$ are given continuous functions which are nonlinear with respect to t and $y(t)$, where $y(t)$ is an unknown function. The known functions are $g(x)$, $k_f(x, t)$, $k_v(x, t)$ and λ_f , λ_v are real or complex constants.

2 Bessel polynomials of first kind

The m-th degree truncated Bessel polynomials of first kind are defined by [4]

$$J_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!(k+n)!} \left(\frac{x}{2}\right)^{2k+n}, \quad 0 \leq x < \infty, \quad n \in N, \quad (3)$$

where N is chosen the positive integer so that $N \geq n$ and $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$. The transformation matrix from the Bessel polynomials of first kind to in N-th degree Taylor basis functions is derived as follows

$$J(x) \simeq DX(x), \quad (4)$$

where D is defined in [4] $J(x) = [J_0(x), J_1(x), \dots, J_N(x)]^T$ and $X(x) = [X_0(x), X_1(x), \dots, X_N(x)]^T$.

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3 Operational matrix of the fractional integration

The operational matrix of integration with integer order for the vector $J(x)$ defined in [4]. Now, we derive the Bessel operational matrix of the fractional integration. For this purpose, can be expanded Taylor functions into an $N+1$ -set of block-pulse function $b_i(x)$ [5] as follows

$$x^k = \sum_{i=0}^N \rho_i b_i(x), \quad \rho_i = (N + 1) \int_{\frac{i}{N+1}}^{\frac{i+1}{N+1}} x^k dx, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N.$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$X(x) \simeq \rho^T B(x), \quad \rho = [\rho_{ij}], \quad \rho_{ij} = \frac{i^j - (i - 1)^j}{j(N + 1)^{j-1}}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N + 1. \tag{5}$$

In [5], Kilicman and Al Zhour have given the block-pulse operational matrix of the fractional integration F^α as follows:

$$I^\alpha B(x) \simeq F^\alpha B(x). \tag{6}$$

According to the above equation, we find the Bessel function operational matrix of the fractional integration. Let

$$I^\alpha X(x) \simeq P^\alpha X(x), \tag{7}$$

by using Eqs. (4) and (6), we have

$$I^\alpha X(x) \simeq I^\alpha \rho^T B(x) = \rho^T I^\alpha B(x) \simeq \rho^T F^\alpha B(x), \tag{8}$$

from Eqs. (7) and (8), we get

$$P^\alpha X(x) = \rho^T F^\alpha B(x). \tag{9}$$

Then, by substituting Eq. (9) in Eq. (7), we obtains

$$P^\alpha = \rho^T F^\alpha (\rho^T)^{-1}. \tag{10}$$

As a results, the operational matrix of fractional integration for Bessel functions is obtained as follows

$$I^\alpha J(x) \simeq I^\alpha D X(x) = D I^\alpha X(x) = D P^\alpha X(x) = D P^\alpha D^{-1} J(x). \tag{11}$$

So, we have

$$I^\alpha J(x) \simeq \phi^\alpha J(x), \quad \phi^\alpha = D P^\alpha D^{-1}. \tag{12}$$

4 Method of solution

To solve Eq. (1) with conditions in Eq. (2), we assume

$${}_0 D^\alpha y(x) \simeq A^T J(x). \tag{13}$$

Then, by using the initial conditions in Eq. (2) and Eq. (13), we have

$$\begin{aligned} {}_0 D^{n-1} y(x) &= I^{\alpha-n+1} {}_0 D^\alpha y(x) + y^{(n-1)}(0) \simeq I^{\alpha-n+1} A^T J(x) + \delta_{n-1} \\ &\simeq A^T I^{\alpha-n+1} J(x) + \delta_{n-1} E^T J(x) = (A^T \phi^{\alpha-n+1} + \delta_{n-1} E^T) J(x) = W_1^T J(x), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} {}_0 D^{n-2} y(x) &= I^{\alpha-n+2} {}_0 D^\alpha y(x) + \delta_{n-1} x + y^{(n-2)}(0) \simeq I^{\alpha-n+2} A^T J(x) + \delta_{n-1} x + \delta_{n-2} \\ &\simeq A^T \phi^{\alpha-n+2} J(x) + \delta_{n-1} C^T J(x) + \delta_{n-2} E^T J(x) = (A^T \phi^{\alpha-n+2} + \delta_{n-1} C^T + \delta_{n-2} E^T) J(x) = W_2^T J(x), \end{aligned}$$

⋮

$$y(x) \simeq (A^T \phi^\alpha + \delta_{n-1} C^T (\phi^1)^{n-2} + \delta_{n-2} C^T (\phi^1)^{n-3} + \dots + \delta_1 C^T (\phi^1) + \delta_0 E^T) J(x) = W_n^T J(x), \quad (14)$$

Also, for solving the proposed equation, we need to define $Z_f(t)$ and $Z_v(t)$ as follows

$$Z_f(x) = \psi_f(x, W_n^T J(x)) \simeq J^T(x) A_f, \quad Z_v(x) = \psi_v(x, W_n^T J(x)) \simeq J^T(x) A_v. \quad (15)$$

Moreover, we can approximate the kernel function $k \in L^2([0, 1]^2)$ by the Bessel functions as

$$k(x, t) \simeq J^T(x) k_b J(t) \quad (16)$$

where k_b is obtained in [4]. Then, by substituting Eqs. (13), (15) and (16) in Eq. (1), we obtain

$$A^T D X(x) = g(x) + \lambda_f X^T(x) D^T k_b^f Q_f A_f + \lambda_v X^T(x) M H_v(x) D^T A_v. \quad (17)$$

Consequently, from Eqs. (15), (17) and collocation points [4], we have

$$\begin{cases} A^T D X = G + \lambda_f X^T D^T k_b^f Q_f A_f + \lambda_v \bar{X} \bar{M} \bar{H} \bar{D} A_v, \\ \psi_f(x_i, W_n^T D X) \simeq D^T X^T A_f, \\ \psi_v(x_i, W_n^T D X) \simeq D^T X^T A_v, \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

$$G = [g(x_0) \quad g(x_1) \quad \dots \quad g(x_N)], \quad \bar{M} = \text{diag}\{M, M, \dots, M\}, \quad \bar{H} = \text{diag}\{H_v(x_0), H_v(x_1), \dots, H_v(x_N)\}.$$

$$X = [X(x_0) \quad X(x_1) \quad \dots \quad X(x_N)], \quad \bar{D} = [D^T \quad D^T \quad \dots \quad D^T], \quad \bar{X} = \text{diag}\{X^T(x_0), X^T(x_1), \dots, X^T(x_N)\}.$$

We can obtain A , A_f and A_v from system of Eq. (18) and with substituting A in Eq. (14), we get approximate solution of nonlinear FVIDEs of fractional order.

5 Convergence

Theorem 5.1. *Suppose that $f^{(k)} \in C(0, 1]$ for $k = 0, 1, \dots, N + 1$ and $Y = \text{span}\{J_0(x), J_1(x), \dots, J_N(x)\}$. If $f_N(x) = A^T J(x)$ is the best approximation to f from Y then the error bound of fractional derivative functions is presented as follows:*

$$\|D^\alpha f(x) - D^\alpha f_N(x)\|_2 \leq \frac{M}{\Gamma(N + 1 - \alpha)} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2N - 2\alpha + 3}}, \quad M \geq \sup_{x \in [0, 1]} |f^{(N+1)}(x)|. \quad (19)$$

Proof. Due to the generalized Taylor's formula, we have

$$|D^\alpha f(x) - D^\alpha \hat{f}_N(x)| \leq \frac{M}{\Gamma(N + 1 - \alpha)} x^{N+1-\alpha}.$$

Since $f_N(x) = A^T J(x)$ is the best approximation to $f(x)$, so we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|D^\alpha f(x) - D^\alpha f_N(x)\|_2^2 &\leq \|D^\alpha f(x) - D^\alpha \hat{f}_N(x)\|_2^2 \leq \int_0^1 |D^\alpha f(x) - D^\alpha \hat{f}_N(x)|^2 dx \leq \int_0^1 \frac{M^2}{(\Gamma(N + 1 - \alpha))^2} x^{2N+2-2\alpha} \\ &\leq \frac{M^2}{(\Gamma(N + 1 - \alpha))^2 (2N + 3 - 2\alpha)} \end{aligned}$$

□

Now by taking the square roots, the theorem can be proved.

Recent theorem show that with increasing the number of Bessel functions, the error tends to zero.

6 Numerical example

Example 6.1. Consider the following fractional Volterra nonlinear integro-differential equation [6]

$${}_0^*D^\alpha y(x) = x^3(-1 + e^{\sin(x)}) - \sin(x) - \int_0^x x^3 \cos(t)e^{y(t)} dt, \quad 1 \leq \alpha \leq 2,$$

with conditions $y(0) = 0, y'(0) = 1$ and the exact solution of this problem for $\alpha = 2$ is $y(x) = \sin(x)$. In Table 1, we obtain the approximate solutions for $N = 9$ and $\alpha = 1.25, 1.5, 1.75, 2$. Also, Table 1 illustrated that the proposed method gives high accuracy with less computational cost compared with [6].

Tab. 1: The approximate solutions for different values of α with $N = 9$ of Example 6.1.

x	$\alpha = 1.25$		$\alpha = 1.5$		$\alpha = 1.75$		$\alpha = 2$	
	Bessel	Ref [6]	Bessel	Ref [6]	Bessel	Ref [6]	Bessel	Exact
0.0	0.00032	0	0.00010	0	0.00005	0	0.00000	0
0.1	0.09728	0.097352	0.09875	0.098663	0.09943	0.099415	0.09975	0.099833
0.2	0.18893	0.185847	0.19424	0.193716	0.19703	0.196812	0.19850	0.198669
0.3	0.27339	0.272375	0.28475	0.283807	0.29143	0.290975	0.29527	0.295520
0.4	0.34999	0.347526	0.36929	0.367799	0.38153	0.380815	0.38909	0.389418
0.5	0.41838	0.412246	0.44704	0.444601	0.46635	0.465333	0.47903	0.479425
0.6	0.47846	0.464013	0.51740	0.513081	0.54506	0.543605	0.56417	0.564642
0.7	0.53039	0.499207	0.57996	0.571968	0.61694	0.614770	0.64680	0.644217
0.8	0.57463	0.512786	0.63452	0.619749	0.68139	0.678009	0.71676	0.717356
0.9	0.61204	0.497956	0.68113	0.654568	0.73795	0.732528	0.78268	0.783326
1	0.64389	0.445845	0.72009	0.674130	0.78632	0.777544	0.84078	0.841470

7 Conclusions

In this work we derive Bessel functions operational matrix of fractional integration, and use it to solve a class of nonlinear FVIDEs of fractional order. Illustrative example is included, our numerical results are compared with exact solutions and with the solutions obtained by some other numerical methods, so that our method faster than other methods tend to the exact solution.

References

- [1] K. B. Oldham and J. Spanier, The Fractional Calculus, Academic Press, New York, (1974).
- [2] I. Podlubny, Fractional Differential Equations, Academic Press, New York, (1999).
- [3] I. Podlubny, Fractional Differential Equations: An Introduction to Fractional Derivatives, Fractional Differential Equations, to Methods of their Solution and Some of Their Application, Mathematics in science and engineering, Academic Press, New York, Volume 198 (1999).
- [4] S. Yuzbasi, N. Sahin and A. Yildirim, A collocation approach for solving high-order linear Fredholm–Volterra integro-differential equations, Mathematical and Computer Modelling 55 (2012) 547-563.
- [5] A. A. Kilbas, H. M. Srivastava and J. J. Trujillo, Theory and Applications of Fractional Differential Equations, North-Holland Mathematic Studies, Elsevier, 204 (2006).
- [6] S. K. Vanani and A. Aminataei, Operational Tau approximation for a general class of fractional integro-differential equations, Computational and Applied Mathematics, (30)3 (2011) 655-674.